

IMPACT OF FOREIGN INVESTMENTS ON ECONOMIC STABILITY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11057160>

Foreign investments have become an indispensable instrument in today's global economy, opening up vast opportunities for cooperation between countries that cannot be ignored. This thesis aims to analyze the comprehensive impact of foreign investments on the economic sustainability of states, their positive and negative aspects, as well as the analysis of factors influencing the results of measures implemented through investment policy.

First and foremost, it is necessary to clarify the definitions given to foreign investments for a better understanding. According to the legislation of our Republic, the following definition is provided: “**Foreign direct investments** — investment at the expense of own or borrowed funds of a foreign investor on conditions of risk, without government guarantees¹”.

In the world and local literature, there are many explanations for this term that do not differ much from each other. A.V. Vahabov gave the definition summarizing their meanings in his textbook. According to him: “Foreign direct investment is an investment that allows the investor to have a long-term ownership of at least 10 percent of the firm's share or shareholders' capital, which allows the investor to exercise effective control over economic activity²”. From these definitions, it is clear that foreign direct investment, like other types of investment, is for profit and based on risk, and unlike others, there is a requirement to have at least 10 percent of the enterprise. It is possible to come to a conclusion about At this point, the question may arise, "why at least 10 percent?" The fact is that the goal of an investor with a share of 10 percent and above is not the financial income obtained from the exchange rate difference, that is, "speculation", but the development of the operational (main) activity of the investment object, its support can guarantee that it is. This means attracting additional capital, new technology and methods and, of course, smart management. The company grows, the competition also grows, which means that this industry develops. The development of the industry means the development of the economy.

¹ LAW OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN “ON INVESTMENTS AND INVESTMENT ACTIVITY” № LRU-598

² A.B. Vakhobov "Foreign Investments" - Tashkent 2010 study guide

Foreign direct investments are made by investing countries or countries attracting investment primarily based on a wide range of mutual interests (in some cases, necessity or coercion). Thus, both sides benefit, where the subjects being investors mostly aim to make financial profits, and the state attracting investment is not limited only to financial gain.

The world's largest states are not only attracting foreign direct investments but also aiming to invest in developing or stable states in most cases, indicating that real investments not only benefit the economy but also bring profit to the countries in terms of ecology, geopolitics, and beyond. Through such investments, developed countries strengthen their positions by directing their neighbors and even the countries closest to them (which could potentially be their most dangerous enemies due to geopolitical reasons) to their strategic orbit.

In order to prove the above sentences, in the following 2 tables, the data from the ratings on the GDP rating of the countries³ and the share of foreign investments in the GDP⁴ are presented together.

Table 1. The place of the G7 countries in the ratings.

Position in the rating	Countries	Share of foreign direct investment in GDP (as of 2022)	Place in the world GDP ranking
58.	France	3,79	7
92.	Canada	2,51	9
116.	USA	1,53	1
117.	Italy	1,52	10
121.	UK	1,43	6
129.	Germany	1,16	4
131.	Japan	1,12	3

³ <https://www.worldometers.info/gdp/gdp-by-country/>

⁴ https://www.theglobaleconomy.com/rankings/foreign_direct_investment/

Table 2. Top 20 by share of foreign investments in GDP.

Position in the rating	Countries	Share of foreign direct investment in GDP (as of 2022)	Place in the world GDP ranking
1.	Cyprus	38,06	103
2.	Hong Kong	33,61	42
3.	Singapore	30,17	33
4.	Hawaii	29,95	-
5.	Malta	26,64	121
6.	S.T.&Prince.	23,35	-
7.	Macao	16,64	109
8.	Mongolia	14,61	124
9.	Montenegro	14,10	146
10.	Mozambique	13,79	120
11.	Sechelles	13,35	165
12.	Uruguay	13,21	77
13.	Grenada	13,16	166
14.	Cambodia	12,13	101
15.	Mauritania	11,73	136
16.	Maldives	11,70	145
17.	Gambia	10,47	160
18.	Antigua & Barbuda	10,49	162
19.	Bahamas	9,73	137
20.	Senegal	9,34	106
78.	Guinea	3,13	100
79.	Uzbekistan	3,11	70
80.	Ruanda	2,99	134

As can be seen from the tables, none of the top 20 countries that attract investment is not among the top 20 countries in terms of GDP, or even among the top 30 countries. The giant seven (G7) countries in the world attract foreign investments in relation to their GDP. However, this giant could not allow the G7 countries to maintain their influence among the world countries, all of them to

enter the top 10 in the GDP rating, on the contrary, as mentioned above, they increased their hegemony by investing in other countries, not attracting investment. Through their capital, not only their own countries are using the potential of relatively backward countries. There may be a number of beneficial and harmful aspects for countries attracting investments. The main advantages of foreign direct investment include:

1. Providing foreign currency to the country.
2. Creating new opportunities through capital inflow.
3. Introducing new technologies and knowledge.

The main disadvantages of foreign direct investment include:

1. Loss of control, possibility of indirect dependence.
2. The possibility of financial instability.
3. Environmental hazards.

From the given information, it is possible to draw conclusions such as the existence of advantages and hidden harms of foreign investments that are not obvious to many, that the countries making investments look after their own interests first, and those interests are often not financial. Foreign investments, like public debt, can be a very strong positive stimulus for developing countries if they are attracted in their own way and for reasonable purposes, with a comprehensive analysis, otherwise, it is necessary to take into account the possibility of economic and political dependence.

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